

Review report on extended abstract titled “Catalyzing Responsible Assessment for Open Science”

Authors (alphabetically by last name)

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Feedback Reviewer 1 Clifford Tatum

ID	Reviewer 1				
	Relevance	Significance	Novelty & Originality	Clarity & Quality of Presentation	Overall Judgement
ID9	5	5	4	5	Accept

Relevance to Conference Themes and Topics

The proposal is highly relevant and strongly aligned with the GraspOS SCOPE+i, particularly in relation to the GraspOS SCOPE+i Assessment Resources. The focus on responsible research assessment (RRA) within the context of open science directly engages a key aspect of the GraspOS project.

Significance

This contribution provides a timely preview of the DORA Practical Guide to Implementing Responsible Research Assessment at Research Performing Organizations and addresses the important alignment between RRA and open science principles. The topic is significant in advancing institutional and systemic change.

Novelty and Originality

The Practical Guide discussed in this proposal was published earlier this year and has been accompanied by a coordinated dissemination plan. While the DORA guide is already gaining recognition, this poster could make a valuable contribution by highlighting specific, practical examples or case studies that illustrate the real world challenges of RRA implementation.

Clarity and Quality of Presentation.

The proposal is clearly written and logically organized. For the poster, the addition of concrete, practice-based examples drawn from the guide would enrich the conference discussion and provide participants with actionable insights.

Feedback Reviewer 2 Thanasis Vergoulis

	Reviewer 2				
ID	Relevance	Significance	Novelty & Originality	Clarity & Quality of Presentation	Overall Judgement
ID9	5	5	4	5	Accept

This poster introduces the DORA Practical Guide for implementing responsible research assessment at research-performing organizations (RPOs), with a focus on aligning evaluation practices with Open Science principles. It highlights actionable strategies to recognise diverse research contributions, promote transparency, and support inclusive, community-driven assessment in line with global RRA efforts. The subject of the poster is interesting and well-aligned with the themes of the conference. The extended abstract is logically organised and clearly written. For those reasons I strongly believe that the poster should be presented in the conference.